

TAPPING TEST AND ANALYSIS FOR DAMAGE DETECTION

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1 Introduction

The tapping test has the ability indicating damage in a structural element due to a localized change of stiffness [1]. The change in vibration signature may be detected by ear or more precisely by measurement instrumentation. In this paper, a tapping test method for discriminating between measurements made on undamaged and delaminated structures is presented. It has been shown that the characteristics of radiated sound from a structure during a tapping are changed by the presence of damage in composite laminate. For structurally radiated sound, the sound field is directly coupled to the structural motion. Therefore, Impact response analysis should be performed. In this study, the radiated sound induced by tapping is computed by solving the Rayleigh integral equation. And the delamination model is used to analyze the impact response analysis of delaminated composite laminate. Predicted impact force histories and sound pressure histories are compared with tapping test data. The results of tests and analyses are presented and it is concluded that the impact force and acoustic pressure data can be used to identify the presence of delamination. And it is shown that the presented analysis model was found to be reliable for predicting the tapping phenomena.

2 Impact response analyses

2.1 Spring-mass model

Spring-mass models are simple and provide accurate solutions. The most complete model consists of one spring representing the linear stiffness of contact law and plate element representing the composite laminate. Fig.1 shows the FEM model for impact response analysis for hammer shaped impactor. The hammer shaped impactor is modeled by solid elements and beam elements. The use of three-

dimensional elements to model the hammer shaped impactor is inconvenient because of a quite number of elements necessary to obtain numerical solutions. And it is time consuming work if the hammer shape is complicated. So the hammer shaped impactor is simplified by concentrated mass to use spring – mass model. Fig.2 shows the FEM model for impact response analysis using general – purpose FEM software [2]. The mass of impactor is lumped at the end of the spring mass, and the other end of spring element is attached to laminate at impacted location. The equivalent concentrated mass is determined as followed procedure. Where R_c is the mass center of impactor, θ is rotated angle from neutral position, I_0 is the mass moment of inertia of impactor with respect to rotation center, v_i is the impact velocity of impact position and $\dot{\theta}$ is the angular velocity of impactor. The equivalent impactor mass is computed as followed.

$$m_e g R_c \times (1 - \cos \theta) = \frac{1}{2} I_0 \dot{\theta}^2 \quad (1)$$

$$v_i = \dot{\theta} \times R_i$$

Where the m_e is the equivalent concentrated mass of impactor.

Fig.1 3-D finite element model for impact analysis

Fig.2 Spring-mass model using general-purpose FEM software

2.2 Verification of spring – mass model

The configuration of impactor and physical properties are shown in Fig.3. Equivalent mass of impactor is 0.092 kg.

Fig.3 Configuration of type 2 impactor and physical properties

The analysis model of the laminate is 19.0×19.0 cm², and the boundary condition of the plate is four edges clamped. The laminate has a lay-up $[0/90]_{2s}$. And the material properties are shown in table 1. A comparison of impact force histories between detail FEM model and simplified spring - model is shown in Fig.4. In this case, the impact velocity is 0.954 m/sec. As shown from the figure, the impact force history computed by simplified spring - model provided accurate result.

Table 1 Material properties

Material properties of lamina	$E_1 = 132.0$ GPa, $E_2 = 8.0$ GPa $G_{12} = G_{13} = G_{23} = 3.74$ GPa $\nu_{12} = 0.3$ $\rho = 16$ kg/m ³ Thickness = 0.14 mm
Material properties of impactor	$E = 207$ GPa $\nu = 0.3$

Fig.4 Comparisons of impact force histories between 3D FEM model and simplified spring - model when the impact velocity is 0.954 m/sec.

The configuration of type 2 impactor and physical properties are shown in Fig.5.

Fig.5 Configuration of type 2 impactor and physical properties

The equivalent mass is 0.956 kg. The type 2 impactor is rotated 15 degrees from vertical line and then released. In this case, the impact velocity is 0.478 m/sec. In Fig.6, the impact force history given by simplified spring-mass model and experimental one are shown.

Fig.6 Comparison of impact force histories between test and analysis for Type B impactor for $[0/45/0/-45/0/-45/0/45/90]_s$ laminate

2.3 Delamination model

To prevent the overlap and penetration, non-linear finite element analysis has been performed to compute the impact response of graphite/epoxy composite specimens subjected to be struck by hammer. 4-node shell elements and gap elements were used to model delamination. The gap elements are inserted along the delamination interface surfaces for preventing penetration of the upper and lower sub-laminates during impact analysis process [3]. Fig.7 shows the schematic diagram of the delamination modeling.

2.4 Comparison of impact force histories between test and analysis

A comparison of impact force histories with and without delaminated is shown in Fig.8 when the laminate has a lay-up $[0/90]_{2s}$. Type 2 impactor is used as impactor. Impact response analysis has been performed when the impact velocity is 0.337 m/sec. From the results, we could know that maximum

impact force is decreased by the presence of delamination. The size of laminate is $19.0 \times 19.0 \text{ cm}^2$, and the boundary condition of the plate has four edges clamped.

Fig.7 Configuration of laminate with a delamination

Fig.8 Comparison of impact force histories for delaminated laminate between test and analysis

3 Tapping sound analysis

The acoustic pressure radiated from a vibration plate can be obtained by evaluating the Rayleigh surface integral where each elemental area on the plate surface is regarded as a simple point source of an

outgoing wave and its contribution is added with an appropriate time delay. The acoustic pressure $p(r,t)$ at the observation point r_0 with Cartesian coordinate (x_0, y_0, z_0) at time t caused by the vibration of the plate is calculated by using the Rayleigh integral[4].

$$p(r,t) = -\frac{\rho_a}{2\pi} \int_{(S)} \frac{1}{|r-r_0|} \frac{\partial^2 W(r_0, t - \frac{|r-r_0|}{c_a})}{\partial t^2} dS \quad (2)$$

Where ρ_a and c_a are, respectively, the mass density and wave velocity of the acoustic medium, $\partial^2 w / \partial t^2$ is the acceleration time history of the plate obtained from impact response analysis, r is the Cartesian coordinate of infinitesimal element at (x, y) on the plate surface. The properties of air as the acoustic medium are density $\rho_a = 1.21 \text{ kg/m}^3$ and speed of sound $c_a = 340 \text{ m/s}$. Equation (2) is put into a numerical form as followed.

$$p(r,t) = -\frac{\rho_a}{2\pi} \sum_{l=1}^{N_x} \sum_{m=1}^{N_y} \Delta x \Delta y \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} W(t - \frac{R_{l,m}}{c_a}) \times \frac{1}{R_{l,m}} \quad (3)$$

Where $N_x = l_x / \Delta x$ and $N_y = l_y / \Delta y$, $R_{l,m}$ are the distance between the observation point and the grid point of co-ordinates $l\Delta x, m\Delta y$ on the laminate.

4 Results

To compare the analysis result with tapping test, a pendulum type tapping test system is set up by the author. The size of laminate is $19.0 \times 19.0 \text{ cm}^2$, and the boundary condition of the plate has four edges clamped. The laminate has a lay-up $[45/0/-45/90]_{3s}$. The delamination is located at the center of laminate and at the mid plane through the thickness. The delaminated area of Del_30 case is $3.0 \times 3.0 \text{ cm}^2$, and Del_50 case is $5.0 \times 5.0 \text{ cm}^2$. In Fig.1, the impact force history given by simplified spring-mass model and experimental one are shown when there is no damage in composite laminate. Fig. 9 shows the test results of sound pressure histories for undamaged, Del_30, Del_50 cases. The impactor is rotated 15 degrees upward from vertical line and released. In this case, the impact velocity is 0.337 m/sec and the equivalent mass of impactor is 0.956 kg. From these results, the measurement of sound

pressure and impact force histories is reliable technique for detection of damage in composite laminate.

Fig. 9 Comparison of sound pressure histories for undamaged, Del_30 and Del_50 case laminates

References

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